

Toxicity Depletion Of Cassava Mash Exudate Using Periwinkle Shells Activated Carbon

David, I. & Kiridi, E. A.

Department of Agricultural and Environmental Engineering,
Niger Delta University,
Wilberforce Island, Amassoma, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
Email: iduaesthr@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Periwinkle shells are one of the most abundant seafood wastes in Nigeria which have not been managed efficiently, causing many negative effects on the ecosystem and the quality of human life. In this study, the use of Periwinkle shells was investigated to provide a calcium carbonate-rich activated carbon material for improving and stabilizing the pH value of acidified cassava wastewater. At 750°C, within 30mins interval, carbonization of the Periwinkle shells was completed. The activated carbon was used to treat the wastewater before release into the environment. Parameters such as pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Salinity, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Total Hardness (TH), Alkalinity, Iron (Fe²⁺), Sulphate (SO₄²⁻), Chloride, Cyanide, Temperature, Total Bacterial Count, Total Coliform Count, Total Fungi Count etc, were analyzed. Testing the performance of the periwinkle shells in the adjustment of the aqueous pH value was conducted, and the solution pH rapidly increased from 4.4 to 5.3. It was proved out that the periwinkle shell activated carbon significantly affected the solution pH value, though it was not up to the NSDWQ and WHO required values. Importantly, the elemental analysis showed that about 46.7% of the sampled parameters were above the Raw sample values. While about 66.7% of the sampled parameters were above the standard drinking water values of NSDWQ and WHO. It was also observed from the data provided that about 26.7% of the total parameters reduced after treatment, but were still above standard values. Therefore, It was discovered in this study that the Periwinkle shell activated carbon only slightly treated the cassava wastewater, but could only reduce the concentration of pollutants below global standards. This implied that further treatment was required before it can released into the environment.

Keywords: Periwinkle Shells, Activated Carbon, Cassava Wastewater, Carbonization, Treatment

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Cassava wastewater is an industrial residue obtained during the processing of cassava into various fermented products such as Garri, Fufu etc. Adewoye *et al.* (2005), showed in his study that the Physio-Chemical characteristics, including Dissolved Oxygen (DO), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), of the cassava wastewater deviated from the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) (1991), maximum limit allowable for effluent discharge into water bodies and environment. Not only does it give rise to the above substances in the wastewater, Okunade and Adakalu (2013), also asserted that cyanide has been always present in cassava wastewater as Cyanogenic Glycosides which hydrolyzes to harmful form as Hydrocyanic acid (Olayinka, 2013). In addition, the degraded cassava peels were said to contain hydrocyanic acid and generated objectionable odor (Okunade and Adakalu, 2013). When waste is not properly managed, it interferes with the environment, which

reduces the aesthetic value of the particular area used for waste disposal (waste littering) and increases environmental pollution (Simon and Adianimovie, 2022). According to (WHO 2006; NIS, 2007), high concentration of cyanide (>0.01 mg/l) in water is very dangerous to human health because cyanide affects the Thyroid and the central nervous system, leading to paralysis. Oghenejoboh (2015) proved that cassava wastewater contained pollutants that are deleterious to natural fish population. High Biochemical Oxygen Demand present in cassava wastewater, depletes the Dissolved Oxygen (DO) needed for the survival of aquatic life in the receiving water bodies (Adegoke *et al.*, 2020).

Though, scholars such as Igwe and Azorji (2018) showed that the cyanide content of the cassava effluent could serve as an efficient source of nutrient to the soil and thus to crops, making it an alternative to mineral fertilizer.

However, due to the toxic materials present in cassava wastewater, simple and efficient technologies for cassava wastewater treatment have evolved. Ribas *et al.* (2010), observed that anaerobically treated cassava wastewater was more stable with the conservation of the mineral of the raw wastewater. According to Ugwu and Agunwamba (2012), observed a drastic reduction of coliform count and BOD in Cassava wastewater such that higher concentration of NaOH led to increased pH. Ensiling of cassava residues, which involves grinding, salting and compaction of Cassava residues, has also increased the anaerobic bacteria through fermentation of cassava residues, thus lowering the cyanide concentration to non-toxic level and decreasing the levels of organic acids (acetic and butyric acid) while increasing lactic acid concentration (Nguyen *et al.*, 1997).

According to Okoduwa, *et al.*, (2017), there are so many technologies (chemical, physical, and biological) that are available for the treatment of effluents, depending on the source. According to them some of the factors that determine the choice of treatment technology include components and features of the effluents. Treatment of cassava mill effluents prior to discharge could lower the impacts on the receiving environment and one of such treatment could be achieved from activated carbon (Okoduwa *et al.*, 2017)

In water-treatment, advanced adsorption technologies have attracted intensive interest from the academic and industrial sectors due to their usage of low-cost adsorbents and simple protocols (Ali *et al.*, 2006). In fact, huge untreated amounts of animal based Shells have been dumped into water bodies in China, Taiwan, and Korea (Hsu, 2009; Wu *et al.*, 2014). In Korea, 250,000 t are produced annually, of which only 50% and 10% is reused in the seeding of shells beds and as agricultural fertilizer, respectively. Approximately 40% of those 250,000t of shells are wasted, therefore, remain to be beneficially up-recycled somehow (Moon *et al.*, 2015). While the above can be said of advanced countries with backed up records, Nigeria has no known record of the amount of Periwinkle shells produced, utilized and wasted year after year. Hence utilization of these Periwinkle shells for cassava waste water treatment will not only enhance the productivity of cassava processing industries, but it will also give rise to a more sustainable environment. As a possible solution to the problem of the utilization of periwinkle shell waste, periwinkle shell powder (PSP), consisting of 97% calcium carbonate, has potential applications as a materials filler as well as in the chemical and food industries and biomedical, energy, and environmental fields (Boyjoo *et al.*, 2014). The aim of the study is to detoxify and degrade cassava mash exudate with the ultimate goal of eliminating toxic substances such as cyanide with periwinkle Shell activated carbon, before discharging the exudates to the environment.

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Animal based shells such as Periwinkle was used to produce the activated carbon at Niger Delta University Amassoma Bayelsa State. The shells were sourced locally from Swali, Yenagoa Market in Bayelsa State. The cassava mash exudate was collected from cassava processing plant and preserved according to global standards also in Yenagoa. The samples collected were safely transported and analysis conducted at Al Barr Laboratories services 24 NIIT road Etegwé Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. The following apparatus were used for the production of the activated carbon in the laboratory. The laboratory apparatus used included Electronic Compact Scale, Vecstar Furnace, Sample Collectors, Desiccators, Sewers, Grinders, Conical Flask Water bath, Electronic Weighing Balance, conical flask

The first step of carbonization of Periwinkle shells was done through washing and sun drying to remove moisture content. They were later introduced into the Vecstar Furnace for carbonization at the temperatures of 750°C and a time interval of 30min. The samples were allowed to cool after which they were washed with tap water then distilled water. The washed samples were then dried in the oven for 30minutes.

After the carbonization stage, the carbonized Periwinkle shells were grinded into powdered form and sieved. The sieved carbonized samples were weighed using Electronic Weighing Balance and introduced into the conical flask. 0.1 mol Hydrogen tetraoxosulphate (iv) acid was added to the conical flask for impregnation/activation. The mixture was thoroughly stirred with a stirrer and then transferred into a hot water bath at 85°C and agitation of 120 rpm for 6 hours. Impregnation continued at room temperature for another 24 hours. After impregnation, the samples were washed with water and then filtered using filter paper and funnel. The samples were then dried in an oven at 110°C for 24 hours (Sait and Derya 2015).

The cassava mash exudate was collected from a cassava processing plant in Yenagoa analysis was conducted at the Chemical laboratory, Niger Delta University Amassoma Bayelsa State.

Batch Adsorption method was employed. For example, 30g of Periwinkle shell activated carbon was weighed and then mixed with 50ml cassava mash exudate in conical flask and agitated in a hot water bath at 40°C and 120 revolutions per minute (rpm) for 60 minutes. At the end of 60 minutes, the mixture was filtered and analyzed for various toxins determination (Olaoye and Owolarafe 2019).

2.1 Sample collection

After collection, the samples were immediately placed in iced coolers for transportation to the laboratory and stored in refrigerator. The water quality parameters dealt with were Physico-chemical and microbiological Simon, *et. al.*, (2023), and were analyzed in accordance with standard laboratory methods. The parameters were; pH, Electrical Conductivity (EC), Salinity, Total Dissolved Solids (TDS), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Total Hardness (TH), Alkalinity, Iron (Fe^{2+}), Sulphate (SO_4^{2-}), Chloride, Cyanide, Temperature, Total Bacterial Count, Total Coliform Count, Total Fungi Count etc.

Plate 1: Filtration of Cassava Mash Exudates with Activated Carbon

In this study, after the preparation of the activated carbon from Periwinkle shell, it was brought in contact with the raw cassava wastewater through filtration, and records taken. These results were compared with the results of the raw wastewater values as shown in Table 1.0 below. The table also presents the efficiency of removal of pollutants from the cassava wastewater.

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

Table 1.0 Result of Parameters levels from Cassava Mash Exudate and Efficiency of Removal

Sample	Raw Values of Untreated Cassava Wastewater Exudate	Efficiency of Toxin Removal (Periwinkle)	NSDWC	WHO GUIDELINES (2011)
pH	4.4	16.98	6.5 – 8.5	8.5
Conductivity (us/cm)	1212	12	1000	1000
Salinity (%)	0.2	50		
TDS(mg/l)	557	54	500	500
TSS (mg/l)	783	46.5	500	500
Total Hardness (mg/l)	10	27	<80	250
Alkalinity (mg/l)	1040	12	--	200
Iron (mg/l)	0.6	9	<0.3	0.3
Sulphate (mg/l)	12.82	28.7	100	500
Chloride (mg/l)	437	61.1	250	250
Cyanide (mg/l)	0.622	29	0	0.3
Temperature °C	25	0	---	22
Total bacteria count (cfu/ml)	62	7.6	0	0
Total coliform count (cfu/ml)	0	0	0	0
Total fungi count (cfu/ml)	15	60	0	0

The laboratory analysis of water parameters was carried out to ascertain the efficacy of the filtration media. This was to obtain an accurate analysis of the cassava mash exudate and its response to treatment with the activated carbon. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to analyze the results with the help of Excel Software. The performance of the media was compared with the Nigerian Standards of Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) and World Health Organization (WHO) using Anova. The performance was also compared with the untreated sample (Raw) using ANOVA. Table 2.0 to Table 5.0 represents the results obtained from the analysis of variance.

Table 2.0: Statistical Summary for the Activated Carbon Shells of Periwinkle and Standard Values

SUMMARY				
Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
Periwinkle	15	5318.291	354.5527	317243.7
NSDWC	13	2460.8	189.2923	92803.82
WHO GUIDELINES (2011)	14	3231.1	230.7929	89987.82

Furthermore, table 3.0 shows that F value (0.611387) is less than the $F_{critical}$ value (3.238096) in the analysis, which leads to accepting the null hypothesis, which implies that there is no significant difference between the means of samples of interest.

The data in Table 3.0 showed p-values (0.547716) that is greater than the alpha level of 0.05, which implies that null hypothesis is accepted and the alternative hypothesis is rejected.

Table 3.0: ANOVA Single Factor for Activated Carbon Shells of Periwinkle and Standard Values

ANOVA							
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit	
Between Groups	210846.9	2	105423.5	0.611387	0.547716	3.238096	
Within Groups	6724900	39	172433.3				
Total	6935747	41					

Furthermore, since the p-value indicates a significant value between the groups, we will have to do a post ANOVA test using two-tailed T-test, two samples assuming equal variances by choosing two groups to analyze first and repeating same with the other groups. This is done to ascertain which group's mean is higher than the other, or if they have equal variances.

Using the Bonferroni post-test or Bonferroni correction, we divide the alpha level (0.05) by the number of groups (3) analyzed to get our new threshold value (0.0167). Table 4.0 below shows the results of the Bonferroni post-test analysis.

Table 4.0: t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances for Activated Carbon Shells of Periwinkle and NSDWQ

	Periwinkle	NSDWQ	New Bonferroni Threshold	True/False Test of Significance
Mean	354.5527	189.2923		
Variance	317243.7	92803.82		
Observations	15	13		
Pooled Variance	213656.1			
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0			
Df	26			
t Stat	0.943517			
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.177051			
t Critical one-tail	1.705618			
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.354102		0.0167	FALSE
t Critical two-tail	2.055529			

The results from this analysis showed that there is no significant different between the means of group (Activated Carbon Shells of Periwinkle) and group (NSDWQ) because the Two-tailed T-test value (0.354102376) was greater than the new Bonferroni threshold value (0.0167). Similarly, the post-test analysis of the Activated Carbon Shells of Periwinkle data and the WHO standards showed in Table 5.0 also showed no significant difference between them because the Two-tailed T-test value (0.471353817) was greater than the new Bonferroni threshold value (0.0167).

Table 5.0: t-Test: Two-Sample Assuming Equal Variances for Periwinkle and WHO

	<i>Periwinkle</i>	<i>WHO GUIDELINES (2011)</i>	New Bonferroni Threshold	<i>True/False Test of Significance</i>
Mean	354.5527333	230.7928571		
Variance	317243.7285	89987.81764		
Observations	15	14		
Pooled Variance	207824.2159			
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0			
Df	27			
t Stat	0.730537374			
P(T<=t) one-tail	0.235676909			
t Critical one-tail	1.703288446			
P(T<=t) two-tail	0.471353817		0.0167	FALSE
t Critical two-tail	2.051830516			

4.0 CONCLUSION

Activated carbon production using Periwinkle shells and the simple preparation processes made it easy for a low cost wastewater treatment process. It can be said in this study that after treatment of the cassava wastewater with activated carbon shells of Periwinkle, a relation was observed in the effects on the parameters. Parameters such as TSS, Total Hardness, Alkalinity, Iron, Sulphate, Chloride and Cyanide, about 46.7% of the sampled parameters were above the Raw sample values. While parameters such as Conductivity, TSS, Alkalinity, Iron, Sulphate, Chloride, Cyanide, Temperature, Total Coliform Count and Total Fungi Count, about 66.7% of the sampled parameters were above the standard drinking water values of NSDWQ and WHO. It was also observed from the data provided that the concentration of some parameters such as Conductivity, Cyanide, Total Coliform Count and Total Fungi Count reduced after treatment but were still higher than the drinking water standard required values, making about 26.7% of the total parameters. However, the pH of the raw wastewater was quite stabilized but not up to standards required. Therefore, it was discovered in the study that the Periwinkle shell activated carbon slightly treated the cassava wastewater, but could only reduce the concentration of pollutants, which was not still suitable to be released into the environment because the concentrations were still above the NSDWQ and WHO stipulated standards.

REFERENCES

- Adegoke, A.T.; B.E. Olowu; N.S. Lawal; O.A. Odusanya; O.B. Banjo; O.B. Oduntan and B.D. Odugbose (2020). The impact of cassava wastewater from wet fufu paste processing industry on surrounding soil: a case study of Ayetoro community, Ogun State, Nigeria. *J. Degrad. Min. Land Manage.* 7(7): 2319-2326, doi: 10.15243/jdmlm. 2020.074.2319.
- Adewoye S.O.; O.O. Fawole; O.D. Owolabi and J.S. Omotosho (2005). Toxicity of Cassava Wastewater Effluents to African Catfish: *Clarias Gariepinus*. *Ethiopian Journal of Science*, 28(2):189–194.
- Ali, I., Gupta, V.K., (2006). Advances in water treatment by adsorption technology. *Nat. Protoc.* 1, 2661–2667.
- Boyjoo, Y., Pareek, V.K., and Liu, J., (2014). Synthesis of micro and nano-sized calcium carbonate particles and their applications. *J. Mater. Chem. A* 2, 14270–14288.
- FEPA (1991). Federal Environmental Protection Agency. S.1.8. National environmental protection (Effluent Limitations).
- Hsu, T.-C., 2009. Experimental assessment of adsorption of Cu²⁺ and Ni²⁺ from aqueous solution by oyster shell powder. *J.Hazard. Mater.* 171, 995–1000.

- Igwe, C.E. and Azorji, J.N. (2018). Influence of Cassava Mill Effluent on the Growth Rate of Two Selected Arable Crop Species (*Zea mays* and *Vigna unguiculata* L). *Journal of Bioremediation & Biodegradation* 9:444, 9(4). doi: 10.4172/2155-6199.1000444
- Moon, D.H., Wazne, M., Cheong, K.H., Chang, Y.-Y., Baek, K., Ok, Y.S., and Park, J.-H., (2015). Stabilization of As-, Pb-, and Cu-contaminated soil using calcined oyster shells and steel slag. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res. Int.* 22, 11162–11169.
- Nguyen T. L.; T.R. Preston and B. Olge (1997). Cassava root silage for croobred pigs under village conditions in central Vietnam. *Livest. Res. Rural Dev.* (9) 2: 12-19.
- Nigerian Industrial Standard (NIS) 554 (2007). NIS. Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality. Document No. ICS 13.060.20: 16-17.
- Okoduwa, S.I.R.; Igiri, B.; Udeh, C.B.; Edenta, C.; Gauje, B. (2017) Tannery Effluent Treatment by Yeast Species Isolates from Watermelon.
- Okunade, D.A. and Adakalu, K.O. (2013). Physico-Chemical Analysis of Contaminated Water Resources Due to Cassava Wastewater Effluent Disposal. *European Journal of Science and Technology* 2 (6): 75-78.
- Olaoye I.O and Owolarefe (2019) Development of Juice Extractor for *Sondia Mombin* fruit. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering and Technology JMEST*,6(5): 10089-10095
- Olayinka, A.S. (2013). Assessment of toxic potentials of Cassava effluent on *Clarias Gariepinus*. *International Journal of Agricultural Science and Research.* 3(3):157.
- Ribas, M.M.F.; M.P. Cereda and R.L.V. Bôas (2010). Use of Cassava Wastewater Treated Anaerobically with Alkaline Agents as Fertilizer for Maize (*Zea mays* L.). *Brazilian Archives of Biology and Technology.* 53:55-62.
- Sait, Y., and Derya, Y. (2015). Preparation and Characterization of activated carbons from *Paulownia* wood by Chemical activation by Phosphoric Acid. *Journal of the Taiwan Institute of Chemical Engineers*, 53, 122-131.
- Simon, C.E., and Adianimovie, S. (2022). Evaluation of Surface Water Contamination by Leachate from Uncontrolled Landfills: A Case Study of Yenagoa Central Waste Dump, Nigeria. *Journal of Engineering Research and Reports.* 22(12): 47-55, 2022; Article no.JERR.88676 ISSN: 2582-2926. DOI: 10.9734/JERR/2022/v22i1217583
- Simon, C.E., and Ogunlowo, O.O. (2023). Seasonal Variations of Leachate Effect on Water Quality Parameters in Etelebu Stream Opposite Abanigi Waste Dump in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Engineering for Development*, Vol. 15(4), December (2023) pp. 24-33.
- Ubalua O. (2007). Cassava wastes: treatment options and value addition alternatives. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 6 (18): 2065-2073.
- Ugwu, E. I. and Agunwamba, J. C. (2012). Detoxification of Cassava wastewater by alkali degradation. *Journal of Research in Environmental Science and Toxicology*, 1(7): 161-167.
- WHO. (2006). Guidelines for drinking water quality, Frit Addendum to Third edition. 1: 211-213.
- Wu, Q., Chen, J., Clark, M., and Yu, Y., (2014). Adsorption of copper to different biogenic oyster shell structure. *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 311,264–272.